

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

Exploitation Plan

Deliverable D7.5

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All work package leaders and co-leaders have agreed to the contents presented in this document during the kick off meeting in March 2019.

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This deliverable summarises the beneficiaries’ strategy and concrete actions related to the protection and exploitation of the project results.

Horizon 2020 is a Research and Innovation programme aiming at fostering competitiveness and growth and increasing benefits to the European Union economy and citizens. Public investment in projects are to be converted into socio-economic benefits for the society, as clearly indicated in the Horizon 2020 Rules for Participation¹, with a clear accent to the beneficiaries’ obligations to exploit and disseminate the outcomes of the funded activities. The Horizon 2020 work programme for this call explicitly specified that project proposals shall include a draft Plan for the Exploitation of Results.

The plan is a strategic document indicating how the partnership establishes the basis for the intellectual property (IP) strategy and exploitation activities, and summarises the beneficiaries’ strategy and concrete actions related to the protection and exploitation of the project results.

2. Conclusion & Results

We have set up a sound innovation management system, agreed on a common terminology among the partners in the consortium, and set up a system for tracking down dissemination and exploitation activities implemented by the partners. Dissemination and exploitation go hand in hand. The plan for dissemination is highlighted in the deliverable D7.3. In that deliverable, the consortium has agreed on:

- A mid-term plan for dissemination activities for the upcoming reporting period (month 1-18).
- A broad long-term plan for dissemination activities, to be revised and updated at regular intervals during the project lifetime.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	Yes
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	Yes
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	Yes
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	Yes

¹ See Article 43 Horizon 2020 Rules for Participation
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/legal_basis/rules_participation/h2020-rules-participation_en.pdf

Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	Yes
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	Yes
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Innovation system

Our innovation management system relies on the following pillars:

Phases	Responsibilities	Description
1. Identifying and securing the foundations.	All scientists	<p>Before the start of the project and during its preparation phase, partners identified the background to be brought into the project and agreed on a set of rules for the IP and innovation management indicated in the Description of the Action.</p> <p>A broad set of rules are in place for the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • joint ownership, • transfer of Results, • dissemination of own results, • cooperation obligations, • access rights: background, accessing rights for implementation, accessing rights for exploitation., <p>The set of rules takes into considerations that the grant agreement requires the consortium full compliance with the grant agreement ARTICLE 29 “ DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS — OPEN ACCESS — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING”.</p>
2. Monitoring of project outputs and impacts	WPL leads and co-leads	Proactive monitoring of research outputs - regular reviews within the work packages. Identifying all relevant IP such as software, papers, know-how, etc.
3. Management and protection of project outputs	Legal advisors of the project partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarify ownership. • Check for “hidden traps” (open access to publications and posters, etc.), which might affect potential patentability or contracts with publishers.
4. Dissemination of the project outputs according to the timeline	All scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular dissemination activity. • Regular record kept at project level of Dissemination (Dissemination master list) and publications (Publication master list).

The formulation of the Data Management Plan (D7.4) is also planned to be ready by 1 July 2019. This plan addresses the relevant aspects of making data FAIR -findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable - including what data the project generates, whether and how data are made accessible for verification and re-use, and how data are curated and preserved. Our DMP defines certain datasets to remain closed according to the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

Terminology adopted by the consortium

The terms “exploitation”, “dissemination” are defined under the Horizon 2020 Rules for Participation as follows and have been adopted by our project.

- **Exploitation** means the use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.
- **Dissemination** means the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including scientific publications in any medium.
- **Innovation Management** (EC Definition) is the “overall management of all activities related to understanding needs, with the objective of successfully identifying new ideas, and managing them, in order to develop new products and services which satisfy these needs”.
- **Results** generated under the project could be any tangible or intangible output, more particularly data, knowledge or information whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not.

Overview of the activities implemented

Phase	Description	Status	Lead	Partners involved
Compliance with Open Access requirements	ESIWACE2 provides open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications through a combination of golden open access and green open access, and it is taking part in the European Commission Open Access Data Pilot for Research Data (see Section 2.2.2 of the Part B of the Description of the Action.). The Data Management Plan has been delivered in project- month 6 (D7.4) and is fully compliant with the guidelines given on data management in the Horizon 2020 Online Manual.	Completed	DKRZ	All
OA requirements implementation	This is monitored by the project office and the WP leaders.	Ongoing	All partners	All
Innovation management system Definition	It is based on principles explained extensively in Section 2.2, Part B of the Description of the Action. It consists of the phases /responsibilities indicated in table 1.	Completed	DKRZ	All

<p>Innovation management system</p> <p>Implementation</p>	<p>The innovation management starts at the point of capturing the creative works and finishes when a product or service is deployable.</p> <p>The innovation management is well integrated in the management structure of the Project.</p>	<p>Ongoing</p>	<p>All partners</p>	<p>All</p>
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Long-term planning of activities in project month 19-51

Regular updates of the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation

The Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation will be regularly updated during the entire project. Updates will be submitted to the EC as an integral part of the Project Periodic Reports, as stipulated in the Grant Agreement.

Major conferences and workshops we took part in/contributed to/organised are listed on the website <https://www.esiwace.eu/events>.

The plan of the activities for the first 18 months of the project is listed in the D7.3, available on Zenodo.

Zenodo as a repository for scientific results

We do not use the ESIWACE2 website as a repository. Instead, resources are available to everyone on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>.

Updates of the Data Management

The Data Management Plan evolves during the lifetime of the project and represents faithfully the status of the project reflections on data management. Updates of the data management plan are thus planned and will be submitted to the EC as an integral part of the Project Periodic Reports.

Intellectual Property Exploitation

A Strategy for the Intellectual Property exploitation (D7.6) will be drafted at the end of the project for providing best practices in capturing and assessing the Intellectual Property and providing measures for exploitation after the end of the project. This will allow the European Commission to assess the impact of the project.

Actions after the conclusion of the project

IPR provisions will remain in force, such as the obligations regarding confidentiality, exploitation and dissemination.

Open access to scientific publications (peer-reviewed publications)

We have established this set of rules for the ESIWACE2 scientists. As general rules: Scientists ensure that publications linked to the ESIWACE2 project acknowledge the name and grant agreement number of the project. The ESIWACE2 consortium privileges Open Access Journals for publishing the scientific publications. A comprehensive list of the journals is provided by the Directory of Open Access Journals <http://www.doaj.org>. Additionally, authors avoid signing any copyright agreements with publishers that do not allow them to fulfil the EC Open Access requirement.

If, for any reason, our scientists prefer to publish their articles in journals which are not Open Access Journals:

- authors pay the extra fee for fulfilling the EC Open Access requirement, opting thus for the so called **Golden OA option**. The publisher can then provide open access to the article and the authors can deposit it immediately in open repositories. If the Golden OA is considered too expensive for the budget of the partner, or if it is not offered by the chosen publisher,
- Authors opt for the **Green OA option**. In this case, authors deposit their final manuscript or the published article in an institutional or subject-based repository. In this case, the publisher's policy allows the author to archive the final manuscript in a repository, before peer review (pre-print version) or after peer-review (post-print version). In order to apply this option, authors first retain their copyright and provide the publisher with a license to publish, instead of signing a simple copyright transfer agreement (CTA).

Open Access to publications: Time requirements

- Scientists ensure that electronic copies of peer-reviewed scientific publications become freely available to anyone as soon as possible and in all cases **no later than six months after publication, as this is a requirement set by our grant agreement with the Commission**.
- If the publisher sets an embargo time longer than 6 months, publications are made available in the form allowed by the publisher in **Green OA mode** by the authors, following the rules set by the chosen journal, as declared in the database Sherpa/Romeo www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo .

Peer-reviewed articles are made available:

- In case of Golden OA: in the internet, accessible via the DOI attributed by the publisher.
- In case of Green OA: in the **institutional repository** of the institutes where the authors work. Scientists inform the project office which repository is used providing a link to the self-archived copy.
- Publications acknowledging the grant agreement number of ESIWACE2 appear automatically in **OpenAIRE** with feed provided either through the publishers' attributed DOI or through the EC portal, SyGMA.
- Information about the publication (screenshot below) is uploaded to the EC portal (SyGMA) by the project office with information provided by the main author(s). These records in SyGMA provide the feed to **OpenAIRE**.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/grants-app/reporting/DIV-675191>. The page title is "New publication". The form contains the following fields and options:

- DOI:
- Type of publication:
- Repository Link:
- Link to the publication:
- Title:
- Authors:
- Title of the Journal/Proceedings/Books series/Book (for book chapters):
- Number, date or frequency of the Journal/Proceedings/Book:
- Relevant Pages:
- ISBN:
- Publisher:
- Place of publication:
- Year of publication:

Below the form, there are two sets of radio buttons:

- Is this publication available in Open-Access, or will it be made available?
 - Yes - available in Green Open Access
 - Yes - available in Gold Open Access
 - No
- Is this a peer-reviewed publication?
 - Yes
 - No
- Is this a joint public/private publication?
 - Yes
 - No

At the bottom, there are two buttons: "Add publication" and "Cancel". A red asterisk indicates mandatory fields.

Exploitation

In ESIWACE2, **exploitation (or use)** is through:

- sharing of project results,
- training, and
- an open dialogue with the climate and weather and HPC communities.

It has been agreed that partners take measures to ensure 'exploitation' of their results by:

- using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- developing, creating or marketing a product or process.

Exploitation of their results can be performed either by single partners directly (e.g. for further research or for commercial or industrial exploitation in its own activities) or by others (other beneficiaries or third parties, e.g. through licensing or by transferring the ownership of results).

5. References (*Bibliography*)

- Section 3 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement.
- The European IP Helpdesk, "Horizon 2020 - A Guide to IP Management", IP Guide, <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/IP-Guides>
- The European IP Helpdesk, "The Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results in Horizon 2020" factsheet, <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/Fact-Sheet-Plan-for-the-Exploitation-and-Dissemination-of-Results-H2020>

- The European IP Helpdesk, “Open Access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon 2020: Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)” factsheet, <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/Fact-Sheet-Open-Access-to-Publications-and-Data-in-H2020-FAQ>

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

Resources are shared in the community via the FocusCoE and other networks we collaborate with. We stick to the principle: "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", ensuring compliance with our contractual obligations on one side and with the maximum openness for the growth of knowledge in the weather and climate modelling and HPC communities on the other side.

8. Sustainability

Tracking past dissemination activities can be more challenging than planning future activities.

We now use the monthly teleconferences with the work packages to remind the PIs to communicate both plans for dissemination and past activities. Further inputs are collected through quarterly activity reports provided by the work packages.

Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects: A number of visible synergies have been created with other initiatives such as the FocusCoE, RDA, EC-Earth, and other projects funded through the same call, or complementary calls (FET, eInfra).

9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is: The general public (PU)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The contents of this deliverable have already been shared within the consortium in the past months, it is part of the set of rules established for the project management. These guidelines were shared at the kick off meeting in March 2019.